

IMPLEMENTATION OF VEDIC TECHNIQUE AND ITS APPLICATIONS

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KEYWORDS

Vedic mathematics,
Veda, Sutras,
Multiplication, Algebra.

ABSTRACT

In algebra the Vedic mathematics is based on the 16 sutras and the 13 sub- sutras. This paper deals with the sutras and also shows how it is applicable to solve algebra problems. Unified mathematics is defined as a situation where methods are understood with reference to one another. Vedic formulas are introduced with the help of examples which can be used to execute various mathematical computations like addition, subtraction, division and accumulation. Vedic mathematics is not only time saving but also helps us to make quick and intelligent decisions for issues of great complexity. Vedic maths is helpful in introducing the burden of poor learning. Vedic maths is often defined as simple mathematics. But it also provides and effective solution to solve mathematical problems.

1 Introduction

The most familiar meaning of Veda is "knowledge". Veda is a Sanskrit word means knowledge. The Vedas are the most sacred scriptures of India and is considered as oldest written text on our planet. The Atharva Veda is sometimes called The "Veda of magical formulae". Vedic mathematics is considered as an ancient system which helps to improve calculation skills. But using Vedic Mathematics general approach and particular methodology, numerical computations can be solve very fast and accurately. Vedic Math Techniques/Sutras have the math tricks for fast calculation in order to solve the questions like aptitude or reasoning problems etc. The entire mechanics of Vedic mathematics is based on 16 sutras and 13sub-sutras. These Sutras along with their brief meanings are enlisted below.

1. Ekadhikina Purvena – Add one number from the previous number.
2. Nikhilam Navatashcaramam Dasatah – we take all numbers from base 9 and last number from base 10.
3. Urdhva-tiryagbhyam- Perpendicular and diagonally.
4. ParavartyaYojayet – Interchange and adjust.
5. Sunyam-Samyasamuccaye – “When the sum is the same that sum is zero”.
6. (Anurupye) Sunyamanyat – “If one is in ratio, the other one is zero”.
7. Sankalana-vyavakalanabhyam – By adding and by decrement.
8. Puranapuranyam – By the accomplishment or incompleteness.
9. Calana-Kalanabhyam – Distinction and likeness.
10. Yaavadunam – “Whatever the extent of its deficiency”.
11. Vyashtisamastih – Segment and total.
12. SesanyankenaCaramena – The residue by the rearmost number.
13. Sopantyadvayamantyam – The eventual and twice the consequent.
14. Ekanyunena Purvena – Subtract one number from the previous number.
15. Gunitasamuccayah – “The product of the sum is equal to the sum of the product”.
16. Gunakasamuccayah – “The factors of the sum is equal to the sum of the factors”.

And the thirteen sub-sutras are along with their brief meaning are enlisted as:

- 1) Anurupyena :- Equilibrium.
- 2) SisyateSesamajnah :-“Remainder remains constant”.
- 3) Adyamadyenantya-mantyaena :-“First by the first and last by the last”.
- 4) KevalaihSaptakamGunyat :-“For 7 the multiplicand is 143”.
- 5) Vestanam :-“By osculation”.
- 6) YavadunamTavadunam :- Lessen by the insufficiency.
- 7) Yavadunam Tavadunikritya Varganca Yojayet :-“Whatever the deficiency lesson by that amount and set up the square of the deficiency”.
- 8) Antyayordasakae’pi :- It means which numbers the last digit sum is give 10.
- 9) Antyayoreva :- At most the rearmost term.
- 10) Samuccayagunitah :-“The sum of the coefficients in the product”.
- 11) Lopanasthapanabhyam :- By alternative eradication and retention.
- 12) Vilokanam :- By trivial examination.
- 13) Gunitasamuccayah Samuccayegunitah :- “The product of the sum is the sum of the product”.

The Vedic mathematical procedure is based on the modern mathematical and the antiquated (old) mathematical systems. Every formula defined as very easy conception and ideas that they will be used to find the issue of variation problems.

2 Literature Review

There are various problems faced by the students to solve the fast calculations, even they know about that problem's solution. Generally, when we solve the problems of competitive examinations computation such as cube root, decimal numbers, multiplication, addition, subtraction of a partial decimal number, division, square root these problem solved by the using of Vedic Mathematics trick or without using of Vedic Mathematics trick in this paper. Normally we solve the mathematical computations, it takes a lot of time, but when we use the Vedic Mathematical methodology we can solve easily. In short we can say that by using of Vedic Mathematical tool we can consume our time for solving the mathematical operations. I hope, this paper will be useful and active in Research work and methods for increase calculation speed in higher level examination.

In 2014, M.N. Dhanave, 2M.A.Kangale have finds that the Vedic math is completely based on 16 sutras, which are objectives and subjective. They are objective in that which are applied to solve our everyday problems and in subjective is based on human mind naturally works sutras.

In 2014,Dr.Urmila rani found that Vedic Mathematics which was discovered by Bharti Krishna Tirtha was helpful in speedy calculations in high school mathematics and it could be developed as a new branch of knowledge by intense research.

In 2016, K. Krishna Prasad discovered that by using Vedic mathematics techniques to solving the problems, we can detract our time. He finds that Vedic mathematics decrease burden of our work load, in quantitative aptitude, reasoning problems and calculations. We can find many short cut methods for calculation.

In 2017, ShuklaAjai Kumar and co-worker analysis antiquated Indian mathematics systems studied as Vedic Mathematics. When we use the Vedic mathematical operations in competitive exams, in higher study, we will solve our problems easily that its makes interest and it reduce times. We can solve our problems speedily and accurate in a short time by using Vedic sutras. Many problems faced by the students while using the Vedic mathematics may be recognize and remediated.

In 2017, Mrs.Gurinder Kaur has studied that by the using of Vedic mathematics techniques we can decrease the work load and we can save our time. We can use these mathematical operation in competitive exams such as finding the reasoning calculation and aptitude problems. By using Vedic mathematics we can examine many short cut methods for solving a large calculations.

In 2019, Poonambajpai has studied in this paper statistically proved that the effectiveness of Vedic mathematics techniques significantly for completing basic mathematical problems for any competitive examinations. More and more use of Vedic Mathematics, cultivates an interest for numbers without any doubts, improve the mind, enlarge the intellect, brain power and evolve the brain by enlarging resolution and attentiveness capabilities. By continuous practice of Vedic mathematics techniques, one can reduce the fear of math and become expert to solve boring and inconvenient mathematical operation in a easy process.

In 2020, Sarita Devi has addressed that by using of Vedic mathematics techniques, we can solve many problems in a short time. With the help of Vedic math we can solve many problems by the best suitable methods.

In 2021, Dr.Vipin Solanki has demonstrated that when we solve the problem of mathematical operations such as multiplication, division, addition, subtraction these all problems can be solve by the using of 16 sutras and these computations are totally based on 16 formulae of Vedic Mathematics. In this paper, we are discussing the importance of Vedic Mathematics. Vedic Mathematics is a primary type of mathematics, but it will be useful in mathematical operations clarification. Many researchers use the Vedic Mathematics tools in their research work and asses mathematical process. Vedic Mathematics is an ancient Indian methodology of mathematical computation or procedure that it was inbuilt in 1957 and it contains of 16 sutras and 13 sub-sutras. In higher level examination students find the solution of problems very fastly within a short time by the using Vedic Mathematics.

2021 K.K. Parajuli had studied that old Sanskrit literature and regenerated Vedic mathematics. He studied that in Vedic mathematics, five formulae are very special which are more considerable. A beginner student can solve the mathematical calculations easily and faster by using these mathematical operations. When we are solving our problems by using the ancient mathematics formulae, we will use the calculator, but when we are solving our problems by using of Vedic mathematical operations, we can solve proportionate problems mentally.

3.1 Multiplication

In Vedic Mathematics there are certain kind of multiplication sutras and sub-sutras to solve the multiplication problems in a easy and best way that we can solve by using these methods Yavadunam Tavadinikritya Varganca Yojayet, Anurupyena, Ekanyuena Purvena, Urdhava Tirayagbhyam, Antyayordasakaepi, Nikhila Navatashcaramam Dasatah and GunijahsApi. By using these formulas we solve certain kind of equations of multiplication in a different way. Here are some examples of multiplication formula are enlisted as:

3.1.1 Antyayordasakaepi

The meaning of this corollary is “Last totalling 10”, it means sum of the last digits is 10, like as 35 and 35, 124 and 26, 72 and 78, 23 and 27 etc. Here the sum of the last digit of the first number and last digit of the second number is total 10. And the left side digit of both numbers will be same. And we will use immediately Ekadhikena Purvena on the left side digits. And when we multiplied the last digits then we finds the right side of the answer.

1) Multiply 395 by 395

Here firstly we apply Ekadhikena on the left side multiplication is $(39 + 1) \times 39 = 40 \times 39 = 1560$.

And in the right side is $5 \times 5 = 25$

And the final answer is 156025.

(ii) To multiply 127×123

As Antyayordasakepi works, we apply Ekadhikena

$$\begin{aligned} 127 \times 123 &= 12 \times 13 / 7 \times 3 \\ &= 156 / 21 \\ &= 15621 \end{aligned}$$

(iii) To multiply 693×697

$$\begin{aligned} 693 \times 697 &= 69 \times 70 / 3 \times 7 \\ &= 4830 / 21 \\ &= 483021 \end{aligned}$$

(iv) To multiply 848×852

Add 48 and 52, $48 + 52 = 100$, we will applied Ekadhikena sutra in the left side multiplication, and we applied directly Anurupyena sub-sutra in the right side multiplication.

$$48 \quad - 2$$

$$52 \quad + 2$$

$$50 \div 2 \quad / \quad -2 \times 2$$

$$25 / - 4$$

$$24 / (100 - 4)$$

$$24 / 96$$

$$2496$$

$$\text{And write } 848 \times 852 = 8 \times 9 / 48 \times 52$$

$$720 / 2496$$

$$722496$$

[Here the left side multiplication is taking base 10 and 1 be carry over as the base is 100]

3.1.2 Yavadunam Tavadunikritya Varganca Yojayet

The simple meaning of this formula is “whatever the deficiency lesson by that amount and set up the square of the deficiency”.

This sub-sutra is applied when we find the square of that numbers which base are closed to the power of 10.

1) Numbers near and less than the bases of power of 10.

For example: find the Square of 994,

Here the base is 1000. Deficit is $1000-994=6$,

Square of 6 is 36.

Now subtract Deficiency from 994 that is, $994-6= 988$

So finally we can write as $988 / 036 = 988036$,

[Here the base is 10000]

2) Square of that numbers which are greater than from the base of the power of 10.

For example:- find the square of 10025

Here base is 10000,

Subtract 10000 from the given number 10025 and get $10025-10000 = 25$

Now square of 25 is $25^2 = 625$

Add 25 to number 10025 = $10025 + 25 = 10050$

So finally we can write as $10050 / 0625$ [Here the base is 10000]

= 100500625

3) This formula is applied to that numbers which are closed to the multipliers of 10, 100, 1000 etc.

Here we integrate two corollaries, ‘Anurupyena’ and ‘Yavadunam Tavadunikritya Varganca Yojayet’ together. For example: find the square of 388

Here the nearest base is 400,

Here 400 behave like as 4×100 . And the number 388 is less than the base 400.

Subtract the number 388 from the base i.e. $400 - 388 = 12$

Again subtract 12 from the number 388, i.e. $388 - 12 = 376$

Now multiply 376 by 4, because the base is $4 \times 100 = 400$.

$376 \times 4 = 1504$

Square of 12 i.e. $12^2 = 144$.

And the result is $1504 / 144 = 150544$ [since the base is 400 and it is multiple of 100]

Another example: find the square of 5012

Here the nearest lower base is $5000 = 5 \times 1000$

Subtract the 5000 from 5012, that is $5012-5000 = 12$

Square of 12 is: $12^2 = 144$

Add 12 to number 5012 that is $5012 + 12 = 5024$

Multiply 5024 by 5, because the base is $5 \times 1000 = 5000$

$5024 \times 5 = 25120$

Hence the answer is $25120 / 144 = 25120144$

3.1.3 Nikhilam Navatascharam Dasatah

The simple definition of this formula is “all from nine and last from 10”. By using this formula in multiplication with the closed base 10, 100, 1000.....and so on, is very helpful. We can solve multiplication problem in few seconds and orally by using this formula. It applicable on those multiplicand which are either less than the base or greater than the base.

When we multiplied the numbers, the number will be greater than the base or less than the base, when the number is less than the base we will take as a negative symbol and we should have to mention the negative sign and when we are taking number greater than the base it will be positive and we have no need to write the positive sign.

For example, the multiplication of 107 by 106 and 17 by 12 are expressed as:

$$107 \quad + 7$$

$$106 \quad + 6$$

$$107+6 \text{ or } 106+7 \quad / \quad 6 \times 7$$

$$113 / 42$$

So, result is 11342

(ii) When both the numbers are below the base

For example, to multiply 97 by 93, it is expressed as

$$97 \quad - 3$$

$$93 \quad - 7$$

$$97-7 \text{ or } 93-3 \quad / \quad (-7) \times (-3) \quad \text{when the base is } 100$$

Here the base is 10

$$17 \quad + 7$$

$$12 \quad + 2$$

$$17+2 \text{ or } 12+7 \quad / \quad 7 \times 2$$

$$19 / 14$$

so, result is 204

90 / 21

9021

(iii) When the first the number is greater than from the base and second number is less than from the base

To multiply 108 by 94. Base is 100

108 + 8

94 - 6

$(108-06)$ or $(94+8) / (-8)\times(6)$

102 / -48 since the complement of 48 is 52 – base 10)

101/52

So result is 10152,

For example: 998×1025 , base is 1000

998 -002

1025 +025

$(998+25)$ or $(1025-2) / (-2)\times(25)$

1023 / -050 = 1022950 since the complement of 50 is 950 for the base is 1000

3.1.4EkanyunenaPurvena

This sutra Ekanyuena Purvena is obtain from Nikhila Navatascharam Dasatah, which means “one less than the previous” or "one less than the one before".

When we multiply any number by 9, 99, 999, 9999 etc. then we applied this formula as:-

a) In the left side digits are get when we applying the Ekanyuena Purvena, that is

(i) For example :- Multiply 8 by 9

Here, firstly we subtract one from 8 i.e. $8-1=7$

(ii) Now we will subtract 7 from 9, i.e. $9-7=2$

(iii) And the final answer of this multiplication of two numbers is $8 \times 9 = 72$

Now an another example: - Multiply 878 by 9999

$(878 - 1) / (9999-877) = 877 / 9122 = 8779122$

And we can solve this multiplication directly by using the Nikhilam Navatshacaram Dasatah sutra as

Initially we will reduce one from the 878 and we get $878-1 = 877$

And then in right hand side we will subtract 877 from 9999 and the outcome is $9999-877= 9122$

And finally, we can write as $878 \times 9999 = 8779122$

2) Multiply 15639 by 99

Here we solve the first step in this multiplication from them the figure.

When we multiply by 99 then the base will take 100 and we can solve as

$[15639 - (156 + 1)] / (100 - 39)$

And the answer is $15482 / 61 = 1548261$

4. DISCUSSION

In this object we have studied that we are using Vedic Mathematics in many Mathematical operations. Initially we discuss the basic definition and meaning of Vedic Mathematics (Veda is a Sanskrit word means “Knowledge”). Here we also compare between the modern Indian Mathematics and old Hinduism Mathematics. And these four Vedas are Rig-Veda, Samaveda, Yajurveda, and Atharvaveda. And this Vedic Mathematics is taken from Atharvaveda. In the Vedic Mathematics, there are a brief discussion of sixteen sutras and their thirteen corollaries. Moreover, we analysis that in this object we discussing the many more mathematical operations in Vedic Mathematics which are addition, multiplication, divisions etc. and how these operations are applicable by using Vedic Mathematics sutras and corollaries with example.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have conclude that for understanding the problem of Vedic Mathematics is very important for us. The study will be helpful for those who design the curriculum to guide the important change to provide the instructor for being extra suitable in Vedic Mathematics. This paper statistically proved effectiveness of Vedic mathematics techniques significantly for completing basic mathematical problems for any competitive examinations. This paper furnish a survey an on the Vedic mathematics. Vedic math is a simple type of mathematics, but it is has very important sutras for doing the computations. Vedic Mathematics is a unique technique of computations which are based on the easy assumption and directive, petition which any type of mathematical issue can be answered orally.

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